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PROPOSAL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN AGROECOLOGICAL-ECOEDUCATIONAL MODEL FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF PEST INSECTS IN AN AGRICULTURAL SETTLEMENT

Propuesta para el desarrollo de un modelo agroecológico-ecoeducativo para el manejo de insectos plaga en un asentamiento agrícola

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ABSTRACT

The preservation of the environment requires considering through a participatory social practice the involvement of all the actors who directly and indirectly contribute to the development of community collective actions on the environment and agricultural management. The research work is subscribed in the educational field considering the fundamentals of eco-education and agroecology, through an approach focused on the qualitative paradigm. The methodological design that included this work was the constructivist investigation, whose guidelines were from Latorre. The proposed actions were consolidated with two eco-educational workshops, visits to the community, interviews and with the participation of all the actors involved. In this investigation, observation was fundamental, since the pest insects and the existing socio-environmental conditions were studied, and it was compared with interviews carried out with the residents. It is necessary to highlight that the eco-educational program was a fundamental tool for the agroecological management of pest insects and for the elaboration of a proposal for an eco-educational-agroecological model based on the community, and its socio-environmental and agricultural needs.

Keywords: Ecoeducation, Agroecology, Insect pests, Ecoeducational Model.

RESUMEN

La preservación del ambiente requiere plantearse a través de una práctica social participativa el involucramiento de todos los actores que de manera directa e indirecta son coadyuvantes en el desarrollo de acciones colectivas comunitarias sobre el medio ambiente y el manejo agrícola. El trabajo de investigación se suscribe en el campo educativo considerando los fundamentos de la ecoeducación y la agroecología, mediante un abordaje centrado en el paradigma cualitativo. El diseño metodológico que comprendió este trabajo fue la investigación constructivista, cuyos lineamientos fueron de Latorre. Las acciones propuestas se consolidaron con dos talleres ecoeducativos, visitas a la comunidad, entrevistas y con la participación de todos los actores involucrados. En esta investigación la observación fue fundamental, ya que se estudió los insectos plaga y las condiciones socio-ambientales existentes, y se comparó con entrevistas realizadas a los pobladores. Es necesario resaltar que el programa ecoeducativo fue una herramienta fundamental para el manejo agroecológico de insectos plaga y para la elaboración de una propuesta de modelo ecoeducativo-agroecológico en función de la comunidad y sus necesidades socio-ambientales y agrícolas.

Palabras clave: Ecoeducación, Agroecología, Insectos plaga, Modelo Ecoeducativo.

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INTRODUCTION

In the world, natural and biological resources are considered a source of food par excellence, which constitutes an alternative for economic sustenance for communities, since they carry out extraction, processing, research, sports and commercialization activities, based on sustainability. human partner; which, in the opinion of Barrero (2000) occurs in a way in the communities of Venezuela.

In this sense, for Santaella (2005) the individual is the only being to resist absolute dependence on nature, among other reasons, because it is not an economic, social, cultural, political and ideological system, with everything and have been able to take for themselves, the possibility offered by the same natural habitat, in creating their environment and developing the social complexity that is characteristic of it, differentiating themselves from the situation of housing homogeneity (spatial) and location, if you want climate of the animals, which seem to carry out great tasks of a supposed collective instinctive work, which denies all planning and conscious thought of man.

From this vision, in Venezuela and on a global scale, natural resources are of vital importance for development, since they are part of an eco-educational system that promotes the development of communities, based on the various activities carried out by the individual, both in the personal, the professional, the social and the cultural, in the search to improve their quality of life.

Hence, eco-education according to Jiménez and Rojas (2012) constitutes a co-responsible relationship between society and education, in the formation of citizens with an ecological conscience, which is essential in the face of the demands and changes that are taking place in the environment. socio-natural, because it requires a harmonious balance between people, needs, use, care and exploitation of the environment.

From this perspective, it is important to recognize ecoeducation as a pedagogical tool because in the opinion of Antunes and Gadotti (2004), education is linked to space and time, where the relationships between human beings and the environment really take place. they happen mainly in the training field. Therefore, eco-education is necessary to bring them to the conscious level.

Within this argumentative framework, in the last 50 years, agroecology has been developing the

fight against pests, based mainly on the intensive use of chemical pesticides or poisons; When they began to be applied, they seemed to be the appropriate remedy to control the damage they caused to crops, therefore, the increase in agricultural production was limited.

But, for the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO, 2003) the remedy was worse than the disease. The increase in agricultural production as a result of the use of chemical pesticides has led to a very high social, economic and environmental cost, due to the mismanagement and use of chemical pesticides of recognized danger, causing multiple problems that affect the sustainability of the agrosystem. biodiversity, the economy, well-being and the quality of life of humanity.

Consequently, insects that behave as pests are related to various human activities, including agricultural production. It is there, where they attract the most attention, because some species manifest as pests, causing crop losses, excessive spending on control measures and insecticide residues in crops that have effects on the health of consumers.

In response to this scenario, the following research proposes Generating an eco-educational model as a pedagogical tool for the agroecological management of pest insects in the Nueva Venezuela peasant settlement.

Ecoeducation

Eco-education, according to Clark (1997), is approached as a strategy to restructure education in all its aspects from the nature and content of a study plan, as well as the way in which students are grouped, the way in which which the teaching-learning process is administered, the way in which the school system is structured and; finally, the so-called "school culture", where the so-called eco-education is based on the theory of living systems.

In the words of Montecinos (1998), the current cultural ideology has tried to replace these fundamental ordinances in the consciousness of human beings with human laws from the political, social and economic spheres. These laws, which have arisen throughout history, have been imposed on the whole of human society by small groups of power, whether religious, political, social, economic or military. So, for the human conglomerate, the norms to be respected are human laws and not cosmic or natural laws; The first should not be transgressed, they are punishable by punishment; meanwhile, the

latter have received little attention. However, natural or cosmic laws are always present, and like it or not, they regularly govern social human development and the future of the planet.

Agroecology as a scenario of human development

The renowned researcher in agroecology, Miguel Altieri, together with Nicholls (2000) express that the scientific discipline that focuses the study of agriculture from an ecological perspective is called agroecology and is defined as a theoretical framework whose purpose is to analyze the agricultural processes of broader way. The agroecological approach considers agricultural ecosystems as the fundamental units of study; and in these systems, mineral cycles, energy transformations, biological processes, and socioeconomic relationships are investigated and analyzed as a whole.

Thus, agroecological research is interested not only in maximizing the production of a particular component, but also in optimizing the total agroecosystem. This tends to refocus the emphasis in agricultural research beyond disciplinary considerations towards complex interactions between people, crops, soil, animals, among others.

According to Altieri (2009), an agroecosystem, establishes that they are communities of plants and animals interacting with their physical and chemical environment that has been modified to produce food, fiber, fuel and other products for human consumption and processing. Agroecology is the holistic study of agroecosystems, including all environmental and human elements. Focuses attention on the form, dynamics and function of their interrelationships and the processes in which they are involved. An area used for agricultural production, for example a field, is viewed as a complex system in which ecological processes occur, such as nutrient cycling, predator-prey interactions, competition, symbiosis, and successional changes.

Human development is focused on social, cultural, environmental and educational environments, which is why it leads one to think about the existence of activities carried out by man in order to sustain his quality of life. These activities include agroecological activity, specifically what concerns integrated pest management within the framework of eco-education, since agricultural communities require educational programs. These settlements demand to obtain knowledge and develop training strategies

on the need to reduce the use of pesticides through crop rotation, periodic sampling, meteorological records, use of resistant varieties, synchronization of plantations or sowings and biological control of pests, and the systems management to improve plant and animal health; and the ability of crops to resist pests and diseases.

There is no doubt that the agroecological management of pest insects, within the framework of human development, requires the application of educational strategies, since it seeks to use the least amount of pesticides possible by the members of the agricultural settlement and apply cultural work from a ecological and environmental vision, in order to avoid environmental contamination, thereby implementing educational plans for the most adequate and safe control of agroecological programs. In this context, this research proposes to develop a proposal for an eco-educational - agroecological model for the management of pest insects in an agricultural settlement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of the Research Scenario

The research scenario is focused on the Cabimas municipality, (Zulia state, Venezuela), specifically the peasant agricultural settlement "Nueva Venezuela" is a rural peasant community that is located on the peri-urban limit of the city of Cabimas, in the Cabimas Municipality, in the Eastern Coast sub-region of Lake Maracaibo, Venezuela. Said peasant settlement consists of several plots or farms with small producers of different agricultural items.

The prevailing climatic conditions in the community is a type of semi-arid climate, characterized by high temperatures, with an annual average of 28.3°C., and low rainfall (728.3 mm annual average), as well as high evaporation and relative humidity (2,227 m.m and 75% per year, respectively), giving rise to very dry tropical forest and dry forest type vegetation. As for the winds, the trade winds that blow in the NE-SW direction predominate, in the period between the months of November/April, they blow throughout the day with some periods of calm and a constant speed (CORPOZULIA, 2011).

Figure 1. Satellite image of the agricultural settlement.

Source: Google Earth, 2020.

The community includes a geographical area comprised of the following boundaries:

- North: Highway G
- South: Highway 53
- East: Highway F
- West: Sector H7
- Parish: Germán Ríos Linares

Design of the investigation

The study that was carried out is framed under the methodological design proposed by Latorre (1996), focused on the qualitative constructivist methodology, which has a holistic, inductive and idiographic approach. Holistic for studying reality from a global approach without fragmenting it or sectioning it into variables. Inductive because the categories, patterns and interpretations are built from the information obtained and not from previous theories or hypotheses. Idiographic because it is oriented towards understanding and interpreting the singularity of social phenomena

Community Access Negotiation

In order to carry out any investigative process, the participation of the researcher is required, the support of the people who make life in the organized community is also essential, so they must be called and taken into account to articulate with the researcher, forming a research group. For the negotiation and formation of the research groups, contacts were established with the inhabitants of the community, elucidating the importance of agroecological pest management for the agricultural settlement.

Selection of Participants

The participants involved in this research were the following: the main researcher, research teachers and collaborating students, in the same way the different people belonging to the community. Being fundamental that this involvement of people directly and indirectly allowed leaving evidence in the community of each of the events that were carried out in this investigation.

Interview

As an instrument for processing the information obtained through the technique, a structured questionnaire endorsed by the Venezuelan Institute of Scientific Research (IVIC, 2018) was used. The questionnaire, according to Chávez, (2007), is a structured instrument or not, which contains a set of items and response alternatives.

This questionnaire is made up of six lines, structured as follows:

1. Educational Aspects
2. Information on the productive unit
3. Phytosanitary aspects of crops
4. Phytotechnical management of crops
5. Biological control
6. Availability

Educational Workshops as Academic Strategy

Based on the results obtained in the interviews, two workshops were designed and carried out, the first called: Ecoeducation, a matter to be learned; while the second was called: Agricultural Zoology from an Educational Dimension, aimed at the rural agricultural community.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interviews carried out with agro-producers of the settlement for the integrated management of pest insects and eco-educational aspects.

The best way to find out what happened in the community was through the interview, since through this the residents commented on interesting data for the present investigation, it should be noted that the instrument used was endorsed by the Venezuelan Institute of Scientific Research (IVIC).

It is important to highlight that an interaction was carried out with twenty-one (21) agro-producers from the community, where they began by requesting their personal data, likewise some informative aspects related to their level of education were achieved: some do not have any type of instruction; others explained that they only had primary education (half); others indicated having completed high school, and only two have a university education.

Based on the interview, the first part contemplated questions in line with educational aspects, which were addressed by asking if they had any knowledge of environmental education and eco-education, where the majority expressed not having this type of training. It was also asked if they knew how to link the knowledge of eco-education and environmental education with agroecology and the management of pest insects, to which they all highlighted that they were unaware of this subject.

Regarding the following question: Are you willing to receive a preparation on Ecoeducation? The answers obtained in their entirety were affirmative.

However, in the second part, concerning the aspects of agricultural items that they cultivate, it was possible to focus that it was mango (*Mangifera indica*, L), despite the fact that in some properties it is not used as a crop, it is present throughout the settlement. Then follows Auyama (*Cucurbita maxima*, Duchesne); Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*, L) also showed a marked presence in the settlement. The papaya papaya (*Carica papaya*, L), as commented by the farmers and the observations made. Lemon (*Citrus aurantiifolia*, Christm) was also found among the crops most used by peasants; melon, (*Cucumis melo*, L), likewise, was one of the most commented on in the survey; like cassava (*Manihot esculenta*, Crantz) Figure 2.

Figure 2: Cassava (*M. sculenta*) crop affected by *Aphis sp* in the agricultural community.

Source: Pascal, San-Blas, Vásquez, Carrasquero Huerta (2024)

In the same way, the peasants commented on other fruit trees with less presence, such as avocado (*Persea americana*, Mill); orange (*Citrus sinensis*, L); soursop (*Annona muricata*, L); passion fruit (*Passiflora edulis*, Sims) and pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*, L). Given these types of crops, there is no doubt that eco-education is a necessary tool to strengthen the theoretical and practical inputs that agro-producers can handle. This could guarantee a higher production and minimize the risks of suffering insect pest attacks. Consequently, if this situation is not addressed from a human, social, economic and educational conception, it leads to a deterioration in the quality of life of the agricultural community.

Another line handled in the interview was focused on the irrigation system managed by the agro-producers, where some expressed using the drip technique, which consists of the use of small plastic containers, such as PEP bottles (plastic soda bottles), said containers They dispense the water slowly. Half of the respondents reported the use of the furrow or flood technique, that is, they make furrows in the soil and let the water run; while others use the sprinkler technique (devices that disperse water), and only one producer indicated that they did not have a defined irrigation system.

Regarding phytosanitary aspects, it was possible to obtain information that a strong majority (98 percent) of the interviewed producers had not received training workshops. Continuing with the phytosanitary aspects of pests, noting those that most frequently affect producers are: the whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*; Gennadius) that afflicts all interviewees; Aphids (*Aphis sp.* Linnaeus) damage most existing crops; and the bachacos or leaf-cutter ants (*Atta sp.* Fabricius) that also cause significant agricultural and socio-economic damage.

It was possible to specify with the observations and the interviews that *B. tabaci* was one of the insects that caused the most economic damage to the producers (together with the Aphids), this hemimetabolous arthropod is a pest that affects many crops, and one of the Mostly committed errors is the indiscriminate use of insecticides, which can cause increases in production costs. In the same way, when applying insecticides, in an uncontrolled way, affectation could occur on the natural enemies of the mosquito, this being able to generate (in the same way) resistance to the insecticide on the part of this pest insect.

To carry out an effective control of *B. tabaci*, it is necessary to know about its biology, habitat, eating habits and its different stages of development. It is

particularly useful to know the stage of development at which the pest is most vulnerable. From this scenario, it is essential to monitor these arthropods for their control, in order to minimize and avoid the use of uncontrolled agrochemicals.

According to what was established by the agricultural community, together with the observations in the field, the pest with the second highest incidence in the community were aphids (*Aphis* sp.). Obviously, aphids are one of the most common pests in the agricultural sector, since they feed on the plant juices and form colonies on it. In the same way, some obvious symptoms were observed on the infected plants such as: deformations, decay and dents in the leaves, in addition to having a complicated biological cycle.

The third pest evidenced by the observations and manifested by the farmers was the bachaco (leaf-cutter ant) *Atta* sp. This insect, belonging to the Formicidae family, Attini tribe, is considered one of the pest insects with the highest incidence in the community, and in agriculture in general, since they can cause a lot of damage in a relatively short time, consuming all the seedlings. from a seedbed or young crop. When they prefer a plant, shrub or tree, they can defoliate it in just one night.

Phytotechnical Management was also addressed in this interview, where the respondents were asked: When do they decide to carry out pest control? Where most answered, manage when pest populations are high. As a control measure, almost all reported using chemical pesticides to eliminate or suppress insect pests. Based on this, the question was asked, how has the use of pesticides behaved in the community? where all established that the use of these chemicals has decreased, obviously not for agroecological or environmental reasons, since some said they bought less pesticides due to the current high costs in the market.

However, addressing the following point: When you apply insecticide what do you do? It is potentially striking that the twenty-one producers surveyed do not use special clothing, some allege high costs, others are simply unaware of the toxic potential (for health and the environment) of pesticides. Likewise, only one reported using equipment (mask, gloves). Only one of the producers said they had received training on the handling of chemicals or agroecological tools.

Regarding the topic on Biological Control, the question was asked: Do you apply any form of biological control on your farm? Only one interviewee

said they did. In the same way, the question was asked: Are you able to recognize any natural enemy of pests? In the conversations it was noted that all the surveyed producers have not received training in the use of biological control agents. Regarding the availability or accessibility of obtaining biological control agents, all stated that they did not have availability.

According to the behavior of the answers obtained, it was possible to verify the lack of knowledge about Ecoeducation and Agroecology, as tools that allow them to cultivate greater knowledge, both theoretical and practical, about techniques, methods, procedures, linked to environmental and ecological work; Therefore, it is perceived that the Nueva Venezuela agricultural community, despite the great efforts and interest that they have been able to show to develop their lands into fertile fields for agriculture, the results are not encouraging for the improvement of their quality of life.

From the product of these results, the decision was made to carry out two eco-educational training workshops, with the purpose of auscultating the reality of the phenomenon studied.

Design and Execution of Workshops as an Academic Strategy

Based on the interviews, meetings, conversations and observations, an eco-educational plan was carried out from an agroecological vision to respond to the purposes of this research, which led to the design and execution of two workshops, the first called: Ecoeducation, a matter to learn ; while the second was called: Agricultural Zoology from an Educational Dimension, aimed at the agricultural community; they were carried out in the community (workshop 1) and at the "Rafael María Baralt" National Experimental University, Cabimas, Los Laureles (workshop 2).

It should be noted that these educational scenarios proposed, addressed, from eco-education: environmental education, environmental impact, ecosystems, conservation and biodiversity, obviously these issues are conducive to the fundamental aspects of agroecology, to then address the biology of the pests identified and a proposal on the agroecological management of these insects. This generated a proposal for an eco-educational model for the agroecological management of pest insects in the agricultural settlement. It should be noted that the duration of the workshops was eight academic hours each.

Figure 3: Photograph of an aphid (*Aphis sp.*) on *C. maxima* leaves. Plant Protection Laboratory, IVIC.

Source: Pascal, San-Blas, Vásquez, Carrasquero Huerta (2024)

Eco-educational Model as a Pedagogical Tool to Address the Agroecological Management of Pest Insects in the Nueva Venezuela Agricultural Settlement

After studying the pests and training the community in the studied phenomenon, it is evident that there is a need to propose some pedagogical tool for a complete approach to the community, where the scientific solutions that can be proposed to the producers are assimilated and analyzed by them in a simple and useful way, not only for productive activity, but also for their lives.

Based on this need, we can propose the creation of a pedagogical model, which can be defined

as particular representations of the interrelation between the pedagogical parameters (Flórez, 1999), that is, that a pedagogical model determines how the relationships between the elements involved in the teaching-learning process.

Rural communities, and specifically the agricultural community of “Nueva Venezuela” have the potential to aspire to sustainability and to the solution of their problems through the application of an endogenously generated eco-educational model, based exclusively on local socio-environmental issues, empowerment. of the community, the revaluation of the social organization, of the cultural structures and of the traditional knowledge of the management of natural resources.

If we apply an ecological principle in the agricultural community, the biological diversity in this settlement must be increased and, managing the productive properties as agroecosystems, by diversifying the crops, the interactions are increased, and a balance can be reached in the community between the prey (pest insects) and predators (entomophagous animals and parasitoids). For this, the populations must be kept in balance (when the ecosystem is balanced), since if there are too many predators, the prey population decreases, and if the prey population decreases, more predators die due to lack of food.

Applying this principle in the peasant settlement we can establish a classic ecological model in the community (figure 4):

Figure 4: Basic model of ecological interaction: Predator-Prey, applicable to biological control in the community

Source: Pascal, San-Blas, Vásquez, Carrasquero Huerta (2024)

In this ecological balance model based on predator-prey interaction, when applied to the community we can say that plant organisms or crops (A) receive a negative impact from a pest insect (B), because these animals they feed directly on it, by herbivorous action, or by sucking vegetable juices; and in turn (B) receives a negative impact from a predatory species (C) that feeds on it. Taking this into account we can say that (C) has a positive

effect on (A) maintaining control over the population of (B). If this general model is applied in the productive farms of the community, control over the pest insects will be maintained, keeping this relationship in balance. Of course, to achieve the application of this general model, the farms must be managed as agroecosystems so that the proportion in the populations is maintained.

It should be noted that complex systems are characterized by being made up of multiple parts that interact with each other, frequently with the additional complexity of doing so at multiple levels. One of the conceptual challenges of ecology and evolution is to understand how these systems work and how robust they are to disturbances (Jordano et al., 2012).

One of the biggest challenges for agroecologists is to identify assemblages of biodiversity, either at the field or landscape level, that will yield favorable results such as regulation of insect pests. The challenge of designing such architectures can only be met by studying the relationships between vegetation diversification and the population dynamics of herbivores and their associated natural enemies in particular agroecosystems.

From this point of view, the aspects acquired through a pedagogical tool, such as eco-education, taking into account the theoretical aspects of agroecology, could generate a more effective and ecological management of pest insects (figure 5):

Figure 5: Preliminary model for the agroecological management of pest insects through Ecoeducation.

Source: Pascal, San-Blas, Vásquez, Carrasquero Huerta (2024)

These previous phases of an educational and ecological nature allowed the construction of an eco-educational model with an agroecological vision, which can be applied to the peasant settlement. Said eco-educational model must propose sustainable activities, based on the socio-environmental analysis of the peasant settlement, made up of the results Obtained from observations, interviews and the ecological-educational models proposed here, the use of soils, the study of crops, the characterization of pest insects, all this in conjunction with the expectations and needs of environmental education of the community.

The model shows the results of this research beginning with Ecoeducation, as a generator of awareness and knowledge, having a main role in this proposal.

Figure 6: Proposal for an Eco-educational model for the Management of Pest Insects.

Source: Pascal, San-Blas, Vásquez, Carrasquero Huerta (2024)

The generation of knowledge and awareness allowed the identification of the phenomenon studied in the peasant settlement in its biological, ecological, productive, environmental and social aspects. Subsequently, by understanding the educational aspects, the model addresses the general environmental problems caused by modern human and agricultural activities. Then it delves into the issue of biodiversity (ecosystems, flora, fauna, interactions, biological and environmental services), agro-production (taking biodiversity into account) and based on this, the specific socio-environmental problems of the community. These indicators converge in the Agroecology section (where the use of natural resources in the environment is displayed). This generates two aspects, the first deals with the traditional control of pest insects (use of pesticides and polluting chemicals), and is compared with the second, which touches on the issue of agroecological control of pest insects (addressing the ecological approach, biological control and use of the ecological interactions of the agroecosystem).

This in turn generated a proposal for an eco-educational-agroecological program for the manage-

ment of pest insects within the Nueva Venezuela peasant settlement, since the inhabitants took advantage of the eco-educational tools to carry out agroecological control.

CONCLUSIONS

It was possible to appreciate, with this investigation, that Ecoeducation differs from other educational models because it is developed in natural contexts, as in the case of the agricultural settlement, where educational activities were carried out, raising awareness and training the inhabitants. Its meaning lies in the fact that it organizes and guides the knowledge of reality through spoken language, observation and systematic reasoning about the practice of the individuals that are taught. Eco-educational learning is not a simple learning that occurs by imitation, or copying patterns, or procedures; since it is a learning that reinforces the acquired knowledge, connecting it to the daily experience and the advances achieved without excessively altering the ecological balance.

Eco-education takes into account ecosystems, ecology. The natural and social environment is interrelated in the physical environment and in the biotic environment, understanding the set of factors external to the organism that act on it. We are in times of planetary emergency since there is a progressive decrease in biodiversity in ecosystems, where the peasant community is part of the phenomenon evidenced, by not using ecological techniques for pest control. All of this progressively destroys the ability to self-regulate, isolating populations of organisms and preventing gene flow between them. The anthropogenic impact on ecosystems produces the mass extinction of species or promotes the abandonment of their breeding, feeding and breeding places.

In the agricultural community, agricultural activities are carried out, which involves not only the production of food, but also a series of processes related to the effects that it produces in society and in the ecosystem. From this consideration, it can be easily accepted that agricultural activities are a fundamental part of human interactions with nature and from this perspective, their analyzes can be carried out from the complex environmental point of view. Agriculture is the result of the coevolution of artificial ecosystems and human cultures.

Agroecological science is inserted precisely in this field of environmental analysis of agroecosystems, assuming the complexity that this implies and

generating new theoretical-practical approaches, which have been changing the traditional agroindustrial thinking of the green revolution, in a more holistic or agroecological thinking.

This becomes notorious in the face of the urgency of satisfying the basic needs of a rapidly growing population in a limited territory, the loss of biological diversity is a problem that cannot be solved in isolation; the sustainable development paradigm implies that solutions to one problem can worsen the situation in others and vice versa. In this sense, the solutions must be synergistic, that is, favor that all situations are solved at the same time.

The issue of biodiversity is important for the management of insect pests, since, in order to have an ecological management of these arthropods, we must increase the interactions within the agroecosystem, in this way biological services will be obtained in the productive properties.

The traditional way of eliminating pest insects, that is, through the use of insecticides, pesticides, and other toxic chemicals, rather than generating benefits, generates a series of serious environmental problems, degradation of soils and their edaphic fauna, death of Beneficial and predatory insects that are ideal for biological control, in turn generate problems in other animal groups such as birds and mammals. Likewise, bodies of water are contaminated by these chemicals, due to the action of runoff, causing additional damage to aquatic fauna. Obviously these compounds are also a problem for the health of human beings.

From this point of view, it is imperative to manage pest insects that is in accordance with the laws of ecology, does not have negative effects on biodiversity, does not degrade ecosystems and does not threaten human health. In this way, the proposal of the Eco-educational-Agroecological model for the management of pest insects proposed in this research becomes important.

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